

Assessment of Non-Governmental Organizations Engagement with the Government in promoting Girl Child Education in Seme and Kisumu West Sub-Counties, Kenya

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Abstract:- Attaining a gender-balanced development environment is an essential step to reaching the worldwide clarion call of “leaving nobody at the back”. Multi-sectorial strategies for gender mainstreaming in training have been widely followed, however, the gender parity gap is protracted in developing international locations. The government of Kenya has partnered with special actors including NGOs in bridging the gender disparity gaps in training. The disproportionately low retention, high dropout, and consequent poor performance in school amongst teenage girls have been a culprit in exacerbating the gender disparity in training regardless of the introduction of free basic education in Kenya. Dropout cases were higher amongst girls than boys, especially in counties with excessive levels of child rights abuses like Kisumu. The position of non-state actors like Plan International is important in offering an alternative and more secure mastering environment for girls. Therefore, this takes a look at the awareness of the programs and roles of Plan International and DREAMS as non-governmental organizations to sell gender equality by upholding the training rights of the women in Kisumu. The primary goal is to study the effectiveness of non-governmental Organizations in promoting the rights to education of young girls in Kisumu County. The study used the Human Rights Approach theory. This observation will appoint a combined strategy case study design to have a look at Plan International and DREAMS’ support applications. The study was undertaken in Kisumu County in two sub-counties Seme and Kisumu West. The study population enlisted 374 young girls and adolescent girls purposively sampled from the two sub-counties who are beneficiaries of the 2 NGOs. To enable information triangulation, the researcher conducted key informant interviews amongst pinnacle management of those NGOs, women leaders in strategic positions, beneficiaries of NGO applications, and Sub-County administrators of Gender, Youths, and Persons with Disabilities (PWDs). A unique sampling technique was used to analyze quantitative and qualitative data. The study’s consciousness became around four signs revealing the findings. Awareness of both two organizations’ activities where the study was carried out reveals majority of the respondents (80.3%) are aware of the operations of Plan International while (18.6%) are aware of the operations of DREAMS and

1.1% are aware of the operations of both organizations: The engagement of the organizations by both National and County government levels; The effectiveness of the support offered to the girl child within the two Sub-Counties named; and lastly how the two organizations engage with both levels of the government to keep the girl child in school.

Keywords:- Approaches, Plan International and DREAMS, engagement, governmental departments, education, child rights.

I. INTRODUCTION

The overall success of the gender-balanced development setup is a vital step to meeting the global clarion call of “leaving no one behind” from a gender lens. “Gender equality in education, as set out in the Schooling for All and Sustainable Development Goals has been an extensively adopted discourse the donors, governments, and Non-Governmental Organizations” (Mundy, 2006, Stromquist, 2008, Unterhalter and North, 2011). To satisfy these worldwide desires, Mundy and Murphy (2001) argue that NGOs are crucial actors in “spreading norms and adjustments on Inter-Governmental and governmental discourse” (Sikkink and Keck in Mundy and Murphy, 2001, p. ninety) and in addition they provide “forceful options to shape world agendas and society (p. 93). NGOs, as “an opportunity space” (Fraser in Magno, 2008, p. 127), are mainly interesting to take a look at because they negotiate their roles with regards to these global discourses and nearby pastime wishes.”

In line with the World Economic Forum’s (WEF) 2022 and the Global Gender Gaps Index [GGGI] document, development is being made toward attaining gender parity, but an excessive amount still needs to be completed even radically to completely near the gender gap. “In 2022 the global gender gap has been closed by means of 68.1% at the contemporary charge in development, it’s going to take like 132 years to attain complete parity” (WEF, 2022). The record similarly shows the following progress inside international locations in terms of gender gaps. The top ten countries have all closed their gender gaps with the aid of at least 80%. Iceland tops at 98%, Finland at 86%, Norway at 84.5%, New Zealand (84.1%), and Sweden at 82.2% raking at position 5. Africa’s top are Rwanda and Namibia which

occupied positions 6th and eighth with rankings of 81.1% and 80.7% respectively.

Sub-Saharan Africa made a development of 1.1 percent over the last 365 days, reflecting wonderful modifications inside the monetary gender hole in nations like Nigeria, Ethiopia, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and Kenya (Kenya ranked variety 57 out of 146 globally) (WEF, 2022). It's miles vital to be aware that in the backside of 10, four African international locations; Algeria, the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Benin, and Mali had been observed. This points to development on the identical time-demanding situations that Africa has to deal with. Measures, therefore, have been proposed to address the gender parity gap that is non-stop in diverse countries.

Gender mainstreaming in coverage and all development applications has been cited as one of the suitable approaches through which reduction in factors that inform, underlie, and toughen gender parity may be addressed. Gender policies internationally are consequently a designed strategy to bridge the gender hole. The gender mainstreaming policies had been crafted and applied via geographical regions in bridging gender parity. However, NGOs as civil society actors have joined palms with geographical regions in gambling the important role in furthering gender mainstreaming through the state" (Rai, 2008).

Education attainment has been one such region of focus on gender mainstreaming since it presents the ladies and girls with the necessities for appointments in different positions that are crucial in ultimate the gender parity gaps like in political illustration. Kenya as an example, has enacted the 2-thirds gender principle with regard to employment, politics, management, and programming. Further, the Kenyan constitution prohibits any discrimination primarily based on, amongst other matters, the gender of someone. other legislation and regulations have also been enacted that searching for to sell gender equality. As an example, the country-wide Land policy gives women's right to own and inherit land.

To completely implement such portions of the legislation, the authorities of Kenya have partnered with exclusive actors such as NGOs in bridging the gender disparity gaps. The National Program on Gender and Development (NPGD) 2019, which spells out Kenya's gender priorities has informed the need for cooperation amongst specific actors in promoting gender equality. in addition, Kenya has installed place catalytic funds together with the Women Enterprise Fund, the Children's Enterprise Fund, and the Uwezo Fund amongst others, that have enabled ladies to get the right of entry to funds to start or build their enterprise ventures without burden. These tasks are anchored in Vision 2030 which is the authorities' improvement blueprint that aims to convert Kenya right into a newly industrialized middle-income country providing an excessive best existence to its citizens with a vision of 2030 in a clean and comfortable environment.

In spite of the efforts installed vicinity, Kenya has been ranked at function 57 in the GGGI 2022 document (WEF, 2022). The evident gaps that hinder the achievement of the two-thirds gender precept have been obtrusive within the judiciary where the Kadhis court docket nevertheless has zero percent of women in spite of having attained 47 percent in different sectors (Institute of Economic Affairs [IEA], 2021). The parliament alternatively has failed to gain the two-thirds gender precept with women contestants in political techniques nevertheless going through discrimination and assaults barring them from being elected to parliament (Okorot, 2021). The imbalance is likewise obvious in phrases of formal employment with poverty being higher among ladies than men at 50 percent with that of fellows being 46.2 percent.

The imbalances were recognized with the aid of the International Gender and Improvement Coverage 2019 which debated that Notwithstanding a modern charter that promotes gender equality and girls' empowerment, gender inequality remains a big problem and challenge in Kenya. The patriarchal social order supported with the aid of statutory, non-secular, and commonplace legal guidelines and practices, and administrative and procedural means for having access to rights have continued to hamper the aim of accomplishing gender equality and girls' empowerment. Modern provisions in regulation have not introduced gender equality in exercise raising the want to expand a policy that addresses the type of manifestations of gender discrimination and inequality.

The statement by the National Gender and Improvement Policy 2019 as said above presents complexities that coping may require a holistic technique to the gender disparity leave. The primary of such measures is to deal with the instructional disparity between ladies and girls as the foundational measures in addressing the disparity. That is important seeing that gender disparity among adults can be traced to the exceptional instructional attainments of women and boys each in number one and secondary colleges. The unpleasant head of gender disparity constantly begins to expose itself among women and boys while reading in college. Certainly, DIFD (2009) points out that the gender hole in training has been growing as children progress through the training device, for instance, Manion (2008), in her examination of the dynamics of women's empowerment inside the Gambia, requires "attention to be paid to the effect of the global improvement and gender fairness discourse on the cognitive and behavioral components of the social practice of character sellers on their social contexts" (p. 44). This consequently, points to the need to take a look at the instructional achievements of girls and boys in their social surroundings.

The elements hindering girls' enrolment, attendance, and retention in school are well documented. Chege and Sifuna (2006), for instance, looked at boys' and girls' education in Kenya, diagnosed proscribing elements affecting girls' admission to the formal education system, stating the patrilineal nature of inheritance which favors boys, the high opportunity cost of girls' training given the vital nature of child hard work for family survival, the belief

that once married women emerge as part of another own family so the investment is lost, and the view that with too much education a girl might also have difficulty in locating a husband. Similarly, GCN (2004) adds school factors that inhibit girls’ full participation in school, along with inadequate sanitary centers and gender-insensitive environments. Further, Colclough et al. (2000), single out harmful cultural values that propel teenage pregnancies and early marriages, Whilst Hunt (2008) factors to extant literature which points to sexual harassment and violence by teachers and boys as principal issues dealing with girls in education.

Different studies have pointed to the wastage in education particularly between boys and ladies as follows. Critical Bureau of Records (CBS) revealed that the drop-out of school teenagers between the ages of 15 and 18 years became 41% (CBS, 2002). GOK (2014) validated that many girls didn’t continue to be in secondary education (57.6% of girls in Siaya and 23.2% for girls in Nairobi). There are several motives that have been pointed out as the perpetrators of training wastage. For instance, a take a look at carried out by ActionAid (2018), discovered that school surroundings, religion, economic strength of families, lack of confidence, and broken families led to the drop of girls to school in eight counties namely Baringo, West Pokot, Migori, Garissa, Kajiado, Embu, Taita Taveta and Isiolo.

These research factors the want of addressing the faculty environment, insecurities, and financial strength of families in decreasing educational wastages amongst teenage women in tackling gender disparity.

Stemming from the above. It is clear that the reasons for ladies’ education wastage are properly documented. However, it’s been located that “few research accounts for the complexities of get right of entry and the interactive, dynamic nature of factors which may make contributions losing out” (Hunt, 2008: 5). In addition, Hunt, has counseled that there have been even much fewer studies on retention, and argue for extra qualitative, smaller scale, nuanced accounts of localized research (Warrington and Karagu, 2011: 301).

These complexities therefore call for re-invigorated multi-stakeholder involvement throughout the country and non-kingdom actors as supplied for in each of the FMG, Gender and development rules, and legislation. mainly, even as the government should play an essential function, the civil society corporations (CSOs), especially NGOs dealing in gender-related applications retain to play a vital function in regards to complimenting the works of Governments (Centre for Rights Schooling and Consciousness [CREAW], 2022).The GGGR (2022) has actually emphasized that NGOs ought to continue to be a key partner to governments in last the gender gap.

Studies undertaken with the aid of Plan Worldwide in Spain, Uganda, and Colombia demonstrate that gender inequality continues to be a great deal part of the cloth of our society. The proof from such studies is captivating, and horrifying, uncovering a complicated thread of discrimination and violence at all levels. “the key to equality is to assign the full-size notion that girls are worth less than boys: a valuation that starts off evolved while they are born and follows them into their grownup lives” (Plan worldwide [PI], 2017, p.3). hard this notion will require among other key steps making sure that girls’ rights to schooling are equal to those of boys because long-lasting answers will come from empowered girls and an empowered society.

Based on the present proof, ensuring girls get to the faculties to study and that schools are safe for his or her studying is a matter of urgency globally, and for Kenya. Between 500 million and 1.5 billion children revel in violence every year (UNICEF, 2009) lots of whom are in schools (PI, 2017). Plan International, an anticipated 150 million girls and 73 million boys have experienced sexual violence (PI, 2013). Half of all sexual assaults are committed toward girls below 16 years of age (International Fitness Organization, 2005; PI, 2013). Reviews from Kenya indicate that children as young as six years of age are victims of rape (Chinyama&Mwabe, 2007; PI, 2013; PI, 2017). Bullying is also pervasive as surveys show that between one-fifth (China) and two-thirds (Zambia) of children mentioned being victims of verbal or bodily bullying (Global Health Employer, 2012; PI, 2017).

Table 1: Transition Rates in Primary Schools in Kisumu County.

Percentage Transition Rates	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Average								
Expected National Transition Rate	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
National Transition Rate	90.12	94.01	93.11	93.62	93.80	95.00	97.54	96.45
Kisumu East Sub County	70.12	69.01	70.22	69.22	68.52	69.90	67.74	67.62
Kisumu West Sub County	72.89	71.15	72.09	72.30	73.01	73.16	71.5	70.42
Kisumu Central Sub County	75.02	75.10	74.03	76.0	77.00	75.01	76.40	75.30
Seme Sub County	71.13	69.03	68.24	70.97	69.99	71.76	68.10	69.0
Muhoroni Sub County	70.34	70.45	71.13	71.00	70.24	70.99	43.99	70.10
Nyando Sub County	74.23	73.71	73.01	72.04	73.00	74.15	46.17	72.90
Nyakach Sub County	73.20	72.98	72.43	72.36	78.05	74.11	47.77	74.00

Source: Kisumu County Education Office Statistics (2018)

From the table it was observed that the average transition rate in primary schools in Kisumu East Sub County was the lowest at 69.04 as compared to the neighboring sub counties, that is Kisumu West at 71.94 and Kisumu Central at an average of 75.80, Seme at 70.03, Muhoroni at 70.40, Nyando at 73.02 and Nyakach at 73.36.

Whereas, Nyakach Sub-County presented the highest average among the rural counties with Seme presenting the lowest. The marked difference between the rural counties warrants research to understand what accounts for the differences and the role that Plan International and DREAMS play in the transition rate.

Table 2: Dropout Rates in Kisumu County

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Average
National Dropout rate	7.30	5.93	4.70	6.32	5.21	5.24	3.32	1.17	4.89
Kisumu East Sub County	21.02	22.42	22.0	23.0	21.52	21.09	20.34	20.18	21.43
Kisumu West Sub County	19.44	10.50	18.53	19.00	19.04	18.95	18.10	18.54	19.01
Kisumu Central Sub County	13.29	13.54	13.24	13.92	12.0	13.52	14.23	14.00	13.43
Seme Sub County	18.53	19.75	20.54	20.34	20.56	20.99	20.00	19.57	20.87
Muhoroni Sub County	17.75	20.50	21.15	19.21	20.52	18.32	20.15	18.00	19.57
Nyando Sub County	19.54	21.42	20.32	19.51	18.52	18.63	19.23	20.07	19.78
Nyakach Sub County	20.75	21.09	21.99	22.44	20.43	20.87	19.60	19.47	20.83

Source: Kisumu County Education Office Statistics (2018)

From the table of dropout charges most of the rural counties suggest that Seme has the very best dropout price observed by Nyakach and then the Muhoroni sub-county. It's far more thrilling that Seme additionally has the lowest degree of transition but the best level of dropout more or less like Nyakach which had the best degree of transition. These exciting data make it worthwhile to analyze the function-played Plan International and Dreams that might be enforcing intervention techniques in these areas. It's miles well worth noting that the Kisumu East sub-county has been studied and the literature has furnished data on the causes of the low transition fee and high dropout charge (see, Airo, M. Sika, J. & Olendo C., 2022). The choice of the two sub-counties is primarily based on their low transition quotes and excessive dropout prices as well as the presence of the two NGOs inside the sub-counties.

The present look hence narrowed down to an investigation of the lessons from PLAN INTERNATIONAL and the DREAMS (Determined, Resilient, Empowered, AIDS-loose, Mentored, and safe) under USAID. Plan International was chosen because it has more than one application that targets lady infant schooling whereas Dreams was selected due to its different recognition of adolescent ladies in addition to its focus on strengthening households with social safety (training subsidies, mixture of socio-financial tactics) and parent/caregiver applications which searching for to create secure environments for girls to remain in faculty. Similarly, the choice of PI is based totally on its over eighty years of straight programming on children's rights. This stands in assessment with the reveal in of dreams which changed into launched in 2014 as a pilot software in HIV/AIDS excessive incidence areas like Kisumu as a result contributing to the essential element of decreasing the HIV burden amongst adolescent women in growing safe surroundings that would finally lessen the training wastages among women. Therefore, the study explored an assessment of non-governmental organizations' engagement with the government in promoting girl child education in Seme and Kisumu West Sub-counties, Kenya.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Non-governmental agencies (NGOs) whose strategic objective is to pursue human rights and push actors to respond to dire wishes of human rights abuses are essential actors. Meernik, Aloisi, Sowell & Nichols (2012) argue that the purpose a few countries continue to conduct or entertain the conduct of egregious human rights abuses yet showcase a negligible 'amount of international opprobrium' is due to the dearth of human rights corporations, especially those more potent human rights NGOs in the one's states.

To rally states and other actors to their strategic human rights objectives, NGOs use a number of techniques or procedures. Meernik, Aloisi, Sowell & Nichols (2012) argue that the important thing among these methods consists of naming and shaming. The scholars by way of analyzing the quantity of software and success of Amnesty International's 'call for urgent movement' technique of pushing via her naming and shaming publicity, determined that this become a critical technique to effectively rallying states, however additionally outside actors' which including the United countries (UN).

Consistent with scholars, a sense of desire in many International corporations, and governments to enhance states' human rights in naming and shaming of exposure campaigns. United nations-affiliated groups, like the Human Rights Council and excessive Commissioner for Human Rights; nongovernmental organizations, consisting of Amnesty International, and Human Rights Watch individuals and governments target some nations for precise interest and condemnation inside the wish that through such exposure, these governments were pressured to change their abusive practices.

Scholars mention that in instances while naming and shaming exposure did not work to correctly win states to examine and defend the human rights of their populations, Amnesty International prolonged her target market to outside actors, portraying the dire state of affairs and attractive in informing and sharing to lobby for his or her actions, which includes via sanctions as passed off in Sudan

for President Albashiir. subsequently naming and shaming is one of the tools utilized by human rights agencies, both inter-governmental and non-governmental. Gender issues represent one of the most critical spheres where several troubles of human rights intersect.

One of the goals of this paper discover the different strategies utilized by PI to rally actors to aid gender-sensitive improvement, specifically as relates to her lady infant schooling programming and advocacy in Kisumu County (Seme and Kisumu West Sub-Counties). At the same time, this is essential insofar as informing stakeholders on the cutting-edge context and what may be achieved higher even through policy interventions, no matter PI's essential function in pursuing girl rights in Kisumu, Kenya, and across 70 different countries, coverage, and studies students are yet to undertake a study of any such scope it would be interesting to research how naming and shaming and the electricity of facts-sharing tools have worked to push for promotive, preventive, and responsiveness of actors in the direction of the right of the lady toddler to training.

Other than naming and shaming and using the electricity of facts, most different NGOs engaged in political sports which are taken into consideration with the aid of the Governments they function in as charitable political sports. inside the Canadian authorities, Arthur & Drache (2009) file that studies and disseminating studies products are essential devices utilized by the NGOs to push for expected coverage reforms, and other stopping and responsive movements on human rights issues they choose from responsibility-bearers, in particular the Governments. They report the subsequent sports allowed by the Canadian government as charitable political acts.

Dispensing the charity's studies, dispensing the research record to election applicants, publishing studies document online, supplying studies document to a Parliamentary Committee, giving an interview about the research document, dispensing the studies document to all members of Parliament, taking part in an international policy improvement working institution and finally, becoming a member of a government advisory panel to speak about coverage exchange. Within the scope of the present-day examination, it is vital to recognize how PI utilizes strategic political sports inside the context of Kisumu County to push for the rights of training of the woman infant.

Finally, a set of programmatic-cum-method used by NGOs to adopt their strategic human rights goals, and push for actors to respond, is through the provision of offerings to the population and groups they work. According to the Fund for NGOs (2022), NGOs facilitate government guidelines to reach far-flung areas and beautify the general effectiveness of social welfare schemes. NGOs perform a spread of services for social well-being both through enforcing improvement initiatives or through coverage advocacy. NGOs contribute to the overall improvement of a network through their engagement in social troubles, and consequently are diagnosed at 0.33 pillar of development. Most NGOs have the following inherent functions related to

them grassroots linkages, participatory method, network engagement, network consideration, and lengthy-term commitment.

Most professionals understand the function of NGOs in all regions of improvement and feature categorize their role into subsequent categories (FundsforNGOs (2022). Developing Infrastructure, some NGOs assist in the improvement and operation of infrastructure by buying land and then using the land for the development of schools, hospitals, wells, public toilets, and so forth that are used by the community at large. In research and development, these NGOs help in improving knowledge of current problems. They expand modern answers based on studies that deal with social problems. Through advocacy, several NGOs strive to persuade policy development in favor of marginalized communities as NGOs are most possibly to conduct rallies, degree demonstrations, and participate in coverage formulation.

There is dissemination of records in regions where the government is unable to reach out to people, and NGOs assist in disseminating statistics on government activities, regulations, and programs. They assist in creating awareness about applicable government tasks through education and capacity building and also provide education and conduct capability-building publications to empower marginalized communities. Facilitate speak: NGOs can facilitate straight conversation from people to the authorities and downward verbal exchange from the authorities to the people. This way of flow of statistics helps in designing higher initiatives and effective rules to be had worldwide reviews from PI (Plan International, 2021; Plan International assertion Submitted to the commission on populace and improvement, n.d.

OHCHR's document on promoting, protecting, and satisfying girls' complete leisure of human rights in humanitarian situations; PI, 2013; PI, 2017; PI, 2013) exhibits that the employer is involved in those sports. but, it has surpassed the attention of researchers who want to understand how those precise services rendered by way of PI contribute to their quest for gender-sensitive development and proper practices, and challenges can be drawn for the betterment of Kisumu County and Kenya as an entire. The researcher tried to fill this gap with the use of PI's proper to equal and equitable human rights of education for girls in Kisumu County.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive mixed-method design. Kothari (2004) opines that Studies on specific predictions, in connection with data and behaviors on persons, groups, or situations describe descriptive research studies. The fact this study seeks the exhibition of data and characteristics concerning girls' education in Kisumu County with a focus on Seme and Kisumu West Sub-Counties makes this design appropriate for this study. The mixed method design enabled me to triangulate findings from different categories of participants; the beneficiaries of Plan International's and Dreams' gender-sensitive programming as well as different

levels of program implementers. Descriptive Mixed Method Design enabled me to collect data from different categories of actors for an in-depth and balanced understanding of the subject.

This study was carried out in Kisumu County. Plan International works in all Luo Nyanza counties, inclusive of Kisumu County in particular Seme and Kisumu West Sub-Counties. consistent with the PI 2020 record, Kisumu is one of the counties going through child's rights violations which consist of teenage pregnancies and sexual and gender-based violence among school-going girls being the highest affected (PI, 2021). The focus on training through major NGOs, with PI, making it her core tool to acquire identical rights for girls, is knowledgeable by the ongoing inequality in getting the right of entry to training even notwithstanding tries to make number one education free and day secondary training backed. Boys have better figures in Gross Enrolment Record (GER) in number one education than girls in most of the ultimate 10 years. After 2003, especially, the distinction has been larger. In secondary education as well, GER has drastically expanded for boys but the disparity with girls has grown to be large except for the gathering of the number one records as indicated above, the look at extensively utilized secondary facts.

Human Rights approach (HRA) is both an analytical framework and a version of Humanitarian Intervention (United Nations Sustainable Improvement Group, 2022). Therefore, to the improvement theoreticians - researchers and academicians- HRA is a framework for dissecting the consistencies and inconsistencies in improvement programs. To improve practitioners, HRA may be a device for imposing an equitable and sustainable development intervention inside a focused populace. This takes a look at hired HRA as a device for analyzing how PI implements her gender-aware applications amongst children, with a unique target being girls. This study used the HRA framework as a theory from the Australian Human Rights Commission (AHRC). consistent with the commission, the main intention of HRA is to convert human rights from in simple terms legal provisions inscribed in prison files into "effective regulations, practices, and sensible realities". The commission states that "Human rights standards provide steerage approximately what needs to be carried out to attain freedom and dignity for all.

Secondary data had been accrued through document analysis from applicable studies, policy files, journal articles, and organizational information. Data on primary and secondary statistics allowed triangulation to enhance the reliability and validity of the findings. The qualitative data was analyzed using thematic content material evaluation to discover the categories and subject matters coming out of the study. Quantitative records have been analyzed via the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS v. 23) and provided via tables, percentages, and pie charts in imparting the diverse mechanisms of engagement through the Plan International and desires engagement with government departments in promoting access to education through girls of Seme and Kisumu West Sub-counties in Kisumu County, Kenya.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The findings of this study have presented data on the awareness level of the two organizations' operations; The engagement of the organizations by both National and County government levels; The effectiveness of the support offered to the girl child within the two Sub-Counties named; and how the two organizations engage with both levels of the government to keep the girl child in school. The findings presented and discussed along the above themes with the aim of assessing NGOs' engagement in girl child education and its implications in these Sub-Counties.

This chapter submits or provides the results of the study. Qualitative information was corroborated with quantitative literature to research the study findings. A wide participation from a ramification of communities and corporations, and fulfillment in network engagement creates the lively participation of numerous groups and stakeholders, promoting a complete and inclusive program. Efforts to train community individuals approximately policy selections to make a factual knowledgeable discussion. Instructing the network about the nuances and trade-offs inherent in training, child rights, and NGO guidelines enables significant and well-informed discussions. This study is also in line with most professionals in recognizing the engagement role of NGOs in all areas of development and has segregated their position into subsequent categories (Funds for NGOs (2022)). For instance, in growing Infrastructure a few NGOs basically help with the improvement and operation of infrastructure these companies buy land and then use the land for the construction of colleges, hospitals, wells, public lavatories, and many others which are utilized by the network for large studies and improvement.

Those NGOs conduct studies and assist in enhancing expertise on cutting-edge issues. They expand innovative answers based on studies to cope with social issues. Advocacy: Several NGOs try to influence policy development in prefer of terrible and marginalized groups these NGOs are most in all likelihood to conduct rallies, level demonstrations, participate in coverage formula, and so forth. Dissemination of facts: In areas where the government is not able to reach out to people, NGOs assist in disseminating facts about authorities' schemes, rules, and programs. They help in generating recognition approximately applicable government projects. schooling and capability constructing. NGOs offer training and conduct ability-constructing publications to empower marginalized groups.

The study is likewise in aid of the to-be-had global reports from PI (Plan International, 2021; Plan global statement Submitted to the Commission on Populace and Development, n.d. OHCHR submission on file selling, shielding, and gratifying girls' full amusement of Human Rights in Humanitarian situations; PI, 2013; PI, 2017; PI, 2013) exhibits that the enterprise is concerned in these sports. but, it has passed the eye of researchers who want to apprehend how these precise services rendered with the aid of PI contribute to their quest for gender-touchy

improvement and what policy and programmatic properly practices, and challenges can be drawn for the betterment of the two Sub-Counties in Kisumu County and Kenya at large. This study tried to fill this gap using PI's and Dream's right to the same and equitable human rights of training for girls at the efficacy of engagement through those variables or concepts; the notice of both Plan International and Dreams approaches for the success of girl child training.

The effectiveness of the guide provided to the girl child inside the two Sub-Counties named; and the way the two organizations interact with both levels of the authorities to hold the girl child in school with the aid of anchoring the examination inside the complete dimensions of girl child schooling engagement, the research envisioned the extent to which Plan International and Dreams methods or practices have contributed to the girl child training within Seme and Kisumu West in Kisumu County align with the aforementioned standards. The overall intention is to showcase the assessment of Plan International and Dreams' engagement with government departments in getting the

right of entry to the education of girls in Kisumu County, Kenya.

A. Are you aware of the approaches used by Plan International and DREAMS to engage with governmental departments on child education rights issues in Kisumu County?

To establish a foundation for investigating the approaches used in promoting girl child education in Seme and Kisumu West Sub-County, the study initially delved into preliminary inquiries. This approach aimed to prevent any assumptions that the role of NGOs is recognized and operational within the selected study areas, and consequently, every respondent had the opportunity to assess and comment on NGO programs. The research questions sought to know the level of awareness of the NGO's operations among the respondents. As evidence, the study reveals that the majority of the respondent (80.3%, n=285) understands the operations of Plan International while 18.6% (n=66) understands the operations of DREAMS and 1.1% (n=4) understands the operations of both organizations as illustrated in the figure below.

Fig. 1: Understanding the operation of the organisations
Source: Author (2023).

From the illustration above all the respondents are in concurrence that the two organizations are at the forefront in supporting the rights of girls to education. As corroborated by one of the key informants who categorically echoed that;

.... Plan International and Dreams have been reaching or creating awareness through stakeholder engagement i.e. public Barraza's, community-based organizations(CBO) through caregivers and mentors, public participation, and publicity through local media for a better understanding of their objectives but Plan International has invaded the community in terms of creating awareness deeply as compared to Dreams.....

Another Plan International beneficiary respondent on the other end also narrated that;

.....I got married when am of younger age and after delivery, I determined to look for casual jobs inside the center so I may want to purchase primary wishes for my newborn and additionally store delivery. I have had enough and concept I would rather face my grandmother and father than stay in these conditions. It turned insufferable for me and while at my grandmother's home, I met a set of volunteers who work with Plan International. They could conduct community meetings and dialogues on child protection and gender-primarily based violence. My grandmother encouraged me to enroll in the Girl Advocacy, a peer-to-peer discussion board for young girls and teenage mothers that empowers young girls and women to rebuild their lives through teenage pregnancy, young marriage, and

abuse and through the support of Plan International under the Girls Advocacy program, I've long past again to high school and am currently in form four. I am very much hopeful that the future is vibrant and I'm doing the entirety in my ability as endorse to reach out to other young girls in my community through community dialogue programs with the help of caregivers/volunteers....." She concludes.

The Girl Advocacy Alliance (GAA) has a specialty of enhancing the economic empowerment of adolescent girls and young women. The undertaking will increase the protection of inclined Girls from teenage marriages and commercial sex exploitation.

B. The engagement of the organizations by both National and County government levels.

All respondents agree the two organizations are in the eye of supporting the rights of girls to education and that organizations are continuously engaged with county government at the early childhood development (ECD) level on matters supporting the education of girls within the sub-

counties. The organizations work closely with county Kisumu County government Department of Education and Gender. The organization also works in collaboration with the national government specifically the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Gender and Social Services, collaborating with both the county and national governments in community sensitization activities and outreach. They also provide training for ECD teachers, National government officials, and the construction of classrooms.

The impact of working of the organizations in supporting girls is mainly through the Provision of support towards girls' education (95.2%), and the provision of sanitary towels (0.6%) while 2.8 % with an aim of keeping girls in school reveals that organization provides an inadequate opportunity to all girls, 0.9% reveals that the organization discriminates the boy child and also its effectiveness is also affected by inadequate support for the government (0.6%), as illustrated in the table below.

Table 3: Support programs towards girl child education.

	Frequency	Percent
Always ready to provide support for girls' education	335	95.2%
Provision of Sanitary Towels	2	0.6%
Inadequate opportunity	10	2.8%
Gender Discrimination	3	0.9%
Inadequate government support	2	0.6%
Total	352	100.0

Source: Author(2023)

The two organizations' Plan International and Dreams programs on reproductive health, social, and profitable benefits of educating adolescent girls and young women (AGYW) were extensively proven. Substantiation debate that further education on girls' detention focus, gravidity, and marriage has cross-cutting benefits for the mother and the child's well-being.

Further, educating AGYW by Dreams has been shown to reduce the threat of HIV on the revision of sexual gestures, in addition to social and cerebral changes like tone-efficacy, and commission. Spending more time in school might increase contact with health-creation safety within schools, and among girls limits openings to interact with men who are not of their age, and with an advanced HIV threat profile compared to the girls. Indeed, with these benefits of education, challenges that hamper access to primary education and transition to secondary school still exist. These supports are the incapability to pay school fees or buy school uniforms and books, limited support from guardians, limited resources within schools, and inequitable social morals in the community position where girls' education may be viewed as less important compared to boys' education.

To address some of these constraints, PI and Dreams have several interventions enforced by the public, governments, and non-governmental associations. Universal access programs through the invalidation of school-free primary education have led to advancements in secondary education enrolments. Training, partial fee payment or fully to school-going girls and their families, acquiring birth certificates, or school support programs. In reference to Zimbabwe's case, a randomized study furnishing comprehensive education support in the form of fees, uniforms, and an academy-grounded coadjutor to cover presence and resoluteness issues among orphans that programs keep them in school compared to those who did not and still, among those in the school, there was no difference in academic performance among beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries.

A respondent who was a KI during the interview argued that;

..... the national government helps them in the application of birth certificates for school enrolments through outreach within the community and this has increased the number of children getting this vital document without traveling for a long distance to the headquarters. Some even lack requisite application documents from their parents and through the intervention of the area National government administrative officers (chief), officials from the registration bureau, and education officials have made the

process smooth and worth embracing by the program beneficiaries and the community at large.....

During a Focused Group Discussion, an adult respondent who is a beneficiary of dreams lamented that;

.....I have been supported by these two organizations as I am a single parent, I had a bright girl and through her, I got economic support through the provision of certified seeds that are favorable to our climatic conditions and can mature within a period of three months, also I benefited through financial start-up support for selling vegetables and tomatoes in my community.....

Table 4: Organizations effectiveness to support girl child education.

	Frequency	Percent
Very effective	177	49.9%
Effective	146	41.1%
Moderately effective	29	8.2%
Not Effective	3	0.8%
Total	355	100.0

Source: Author (2023)

One respondent who is a beneficiary of both programs echoed that;

..... I come from single parenthood and when given things like sanitary towels I end up sharing them with my mother who doesn't have the capacity to buy the pads but just survive on tattered clothes and old mattresses as an alternative for survival. I am happy Plan International and Dreams organizations have changed my mother's life and I can have the freedom to interact freely with other age-mates within the society. Initially, people tend to mock me and my mother but through the two organizations' interventions, I can go to school and have something to eat at home after school. Finally, I can say organizational approaches are effective and have made us smile.....

The study also found that early pregnancies and early marriages through productive health education awareness that is cutting across the parents, caregivers, mentors, and girls have been effective. The girls-to-boys ratio enrolment in school also increased as exhibited in the course of the investigation that there are many girls in the majority of the schools within the area of study as compared to boys whose number was low.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the results have shown challenges in the assessment of the Plan International and Dreams programs. Community, NGOs, and government relation is important for the success of girl child education, the majority of respondents are aware of Plan International and Dreams in their communities. The presence of a clear, locally relevant girl child education and support and unlimited breadth of community engagement(chiefs), as envisioned by both the Government and the NGO policy, further hinder girl child rights in education acquisition. Most importantly, there is

C. The effectiveness of the support offered to the girl child within the two Sub-Counties

This study reveals that a chunk of 49.9% of the respondents rate the organization's effectiveness in support for girls retention in schools through education in Seme and Kisumu West sub-counties through various interventions like provision of sanitary packages, school uniforms and stationaries, fees payment, parental economic support, education on reproductive health and mentorship programs as being very effective, 41.1% rate them as effective, 8.2% moderately effective and 0.8% Not effective as illustrated in the table below.

more of education and awareness creation about Plan International and Dreams in the community, contributing to effective community engagement. In a nutshell, the study emphasizes the need for the total inclusion of other donors and stakeholders in improving community education awareness and increasing community engagement platforms. The above steps are important for the assessment of the successful implementation in promoting girl child safety rights and education safety and order in schools within Seme and Kisumu West Sub-Counties.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Need for holistic Campaigns:** creating a holistic campaign focused on Plan International and Dreams programs in the two Sub-Counties and the campaigns should target all stakeholders involved by explaining the principles and benefits of Plan International and Dreams and discrediting the myths.
- **Need to devolve the approaches:** working together with the local communities and government agencies i.e. paralegals to come up with a clear Girl child rights education strategy and the strategy to outline the clear aims, objectives, programs, and duties for all parties involved and increase donors.
- **Need to Enhance Community and Stakeholders Engagement avenues:** Encourage and build more platforms such as Chief Barraza's, and caregivers/mentors' programs and ensure periodic meetings or engagements that address girl child rights in education.

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DECLARATION

I declare that this is my research and was scientifically undertaken. There was no form of monetary support and no subject was influenced by any interests beyond the academic sphere.

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